

COUNTRY FOOD CARGO

Transport Infrastructure and
Food Sovereignty in Nunavut

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INTRODUCTION

In Nunavut, much of the new infrastructure being built is designed to support various resource extraction projects rather than essential needs like clean water, food, housing, and stable incomes. My research focuses on how residents in the Qikiqtani region of Nunavut envision the future of their communities and how these ideas connect to the transportation infrastructure being developed today. Specifically, I explore the link between transportation and country food—traditional foods like caribou, fish, and seal—and how this relationship shapes the future of Nunavut. Guided by community members, my work highlights where decision-makers can better prioritize local needs and support for hunters, harvesters, and those who rely on country food.

How I Conducted My Research

I first visited Iqaluit and Pond Inlet in May and June 2022. After asking residents and local organizations which topics are currently of most concern in Nunavut, I decided to focus on how transportation infrastructure affects food sovereignty in the territory. Once I received my research license from the Nunavut Research Institute, I returned for further research between August 2022 and December 2023. Over three separate stays, totaling 12 months, I expanded my work to include five communities: Iqaluit, Kimmirut, Pond Inlet, Resolute Bay, and Grise Fiord.

During my time in these communities, I visited each location at least twice. I attended meetings, workshops, cultural events, hunting trips, concerts, and town hall gatherings. I also volunteered at a local food center, organized three future-planning workshops, and held two focus groups. In total, I conducted about 170 interviews, with more than 60 recorded. I spoke with a wide range of people: members of Hunters and Trappers Organizations, the Government of Nunavut, Inuit organizations, local nonprofits, Nunavut Arctic College employees, airport and shipping workers, Coast Guard staff, students, and new residents who recently moved to work in the region.

Why This Research Matters

Food sovereignty—the ability of communities to control their own food systems—is an issue that affects everyone in Nunavut. For many people, store-bought food is expensive and not always available, making country food even more important. However, the ability to harvest, share, and distribute country food depends on many factors, including transportation networks, fuel costs, government policies, and climate change.

This research highlights how transportation infrastructure can better support local food systems and ensure that Nunavummiut voices are heard in decision-making.

The following pages include quotes from community members across the five communities where I conducted my research. While these quotes reflect a range of perspectives, they are a selection of the many voices, stories, and opinions I heard. The quotes have been organized into four key themes:

1. Food sovereignty and access to country food – Challenges in how Nunavummiut obtain, share, and rely on country food.

2. Transportation infrastructure and its impact on food sovereignty – How air, sea, and land transportation affect the movement of food, supplies, and people.

3. Economic and policy considerations – The role of government programs, subsidies, and local initiatives in supporting food security and transportation.

4. Future directions and community priorities – Ideas from community members on how to strengthen Nunavut’s food systems and transportation networks for future generations.

Understanding these issues is essential for ensuring that infrastructure development in Nunavut meets the needs of its people. By listening to the experiences and ideas of community members, decision-makers can take steps to improve food security, support sustainable transportation, and build a future that reflects the priorities of Nunavummiut.

MAIN THEMES AND TAKEAWAYS

1. Food Sovereignty and Access to Country Food

There is increasing emphasis on food sovereignty, which includes the right to healthy, culturally appropriate food harvested through sustainable methods. Country food is more than just food; it strengthens cultural identity and community connections. The conversation around food security and sovereignty in Nunavut is inherently connected to the logistics of transportation.

“It makes you feel good too, when you share it to the Elders and give it away. Makes the food last longer, when it’s shared, because it’s spread out and it’s feeding other people.”

– Hunter, Iqaluit,
February 2023.

The following are some of the main challenges highlighted by community members:

» **Barriers to Access:** Country food is hard to obtain due to disconnected sharing networks, no dedicated stores, no way to connect with sellers (no internet access, limited financial means), and limited species availability (e.g., caribou, narwhal, muskox).

“The two of us don’t really have barriers to go out and get country food like some people do, because of the boat and he has the transportation and the knowledge to do it. Whereas some people just don’t have the means or the know-how.”

– Jeanine Nowdluk,
Iqaluit, February 2023.

“I got nothing to use back here in Iqaluit, so I don’t go hunting here. Only when I go Pang. No skidoo, no ATV, no hunting partners...”

– Resident of Iqaluit, February 2023.

“If we have a hard time catching one certain animal, and one community sees more of this animal and some communities would want to trade, it would be a good way for communities to get different country food, help each other out. And like everyone else, you get tired of eating the same thing over and over, so we would trade country food.”

- Mark Amarualik,
Resolute Bay, April 2023.

» **High Cost of Harvesting:** Hunting is expensive, making it difficult for many residents to afford the materials for hunting, or have time off work to hunt. The NTI and Baffinland gas vouchers have been very helpful, as well as the Nunavut Harvesters Support Program and Nauttiqsuqtiit.

“To be able to go hunting, it’s very expensive. The boat, outboard, the ski-doo, the four-wheeler, the guns, the ammunition, and then the food to go out with. If you’re going to be going out like approximately a week to two weeks, it’s going to cost you a minimum of \$5,000 just to go out there. Because the fuel that you need to be on for that long, the food that you leave for that long, the ammunition, and anything that helps you need to be out there. That’s how much it costs.”

- Simeonie Akpalialuk,
Iqaluit, February 2023.

» **Commercial Sale and Distribution**

Challenges: While legal, selling country food commercially is financially difficult due to high cargo costs and limited subsidies. Stigma is still attached to those who sell instead of sharing, though selling country food is becoming more common. However, delays, losses, and damage to country food shipments are common, leading to spoilage and financial losses.

“We have tried to order [country food] before and there was a cardboard box and it had some holes and a few openings and that had a lot of problems. It was also freezer-burnt. We couldn't eat it. It was no good because it was freezer burnt. No money back, nothing.”

– Peter Inootik,
Pond Inlet, March 2023.

“One thing we need is a new cargo facility because now there's a fight for the perishable stuff and the increase of just regular other goods that are coming through the airport and the provider just can't manage it all without damages being incurred. (...) If the supply chain was better modified for [South to North movement] there could be maybe some improvements you see on the quality of food when it ends up in the consumer here.”

– Paul Crenson, Government of Nunavut Manager of Airport Operations, Iqaluit, December 2023.

» **Community Freezers and Storage:** Essential but often unreliable due to maintenance issues and lack of capacity. Long periods of freezer-outage make storage a challenge, and limit who can store country food. Functioning freezers are becoming more important with climate change.

“And then there is the added dynamic of climate change warming things up and this affects choice too because not everything can be stored for the same amount of time when it’s not cold anymore. It takes a lot of planning.”

– Government of Nunavut employee, Iqaluit, May 2022.

“There’s not much freezer space up here at the airports. And they send it during winter times, they should at least put it in a bin instead of a cardboard box because you can just put it outside and let it freeze.”

– Peter Inootik, Pond Inlet, March 2023.

2. Transportation

Infrastructure and Its Impact on Food Sovereignty

Transportation is crucial for both delivering store-bought food and for distributing country food. The long distances, Arctic climate, and limited capacities in communities make providing and maintaining infrastructure a challenge. Each community relies on their own infrastructure to survive, which is both limited and unreliable.

“I mean, you want to support food security in Nunavut? Great. How are you going to get it here? Food and transportation go hand in hand, even country food.”

– Resident of Kimmirut, March 2023.

Here are some of the key challenges raised by community members:

» **Reliability Issues:** Dependence on air transport and sea lift, which are often unreliable due to weather, mechanical failures, and high costs.

“Air transportation is a lifeline but it’s also a headache.”

– Government of Nunavut employee, May 2022.

“I’m anxious for the runway to be improved or relocated to a better spot, because we are not getting proper service yet.”

– Larry Audlaluk, Grise Fiord, April 2023.

» **Runways and Aircraft:** The type of runway (gravel vs. paved) greatly impacts the size and type of aircraft that can land, which in turn affects a community's connectivity, cargo capacity, and overall economic opportunities. Jets with gravel capacity are being phased out, but gravel runways are most suitable for Nunavut's climate and community sizes. There is one company, Deutsche Aircraft, which is now specializing in gravel aircraft for the Canadian market.

“We’re still running on gravel runways and specialized equipment, even the modern equipment that will fly now, the ATR turboprops that we operate, we have to invest heavily in those aircraft for them to be able to fly into the North because they need special skins on the belly of the aircraft. They have to have special deflection panels around the wheels, and they have to have unique piloting skills and training to land in the North because there is gravel. And gravel isn’t kind.”

– Michael Rodyniuk, former Canadian North CEO, Iqaluit, May 2023.

“It seems like a gravel runway would be difficult to maintain, but they’re actually less challenging to maintain.” “Even more so up here in the Arctic where there’s much more movement in the ground with the thaw. The life cycle of something paved is going to be a lot shorter because of the geological conditions that exist in the permafrost.” “These two runways that we have, that are paved, both have severe challenges.”

– John Hawkins, Assistant Deputy Minister of Transportation at Government of Nunavut, and Paul Crenson, Government of Nunavut Manager of Airport Operations, Iqaluit, December 2023.

» **Centralization in Iqaluit:** Air services are increasingly focused on Iqaluit, making inter-community travel and trade more expensive and logistically challenging. This development does not match Nunavut’s supposed policy of decentralization of services.

“Part of the problem about what you’re saying in the milk run is, yeah, okay, maybe it works, but I don’t know your data on how full your planes are. But for example, now, we have family in Qikiqtarjuaq. They want to go to Pangnirtung. Before, with the milk run, you were there. Now, what you have to do, the flight costs around \$4,000 to go to Qik to Pang. You’ve got to go from Qik to here [Iqaluit], overnight here, then to Pang. So that’s not helping the community. To me, I mean, because I live in Pang, that was a great run. And it was full. So now, if you’re going individual, you’re not filling your plane.”

– Resident of Iqaluit,
Canadian North Open
House, May 2023.

» **Country Food Shipping Costs and Policies:**

Canadian North’s country food flat rate (\$1.31/kg) is extremely helpful. However, the flat rate benefits individuals but excludes businesses, making it difficult to distribute food commercially, and limiting harvesters’ economic engagement. Canadian North’s monopoly leaves harvesters with no choice when sending country food between communities, but because their planes must deliver cargo to communities as well, country food is not prioritized and often gets lost, or spoils before it arrives.

“Here in Pond Inlet and other places up here, it takes a while to get things here. And planes don’t take everything. They usually try to take the first priority is people’s luggage, mostly, when there’s cargo planes they try to bring everything but when they put it on storage, when they’re trying to send it here, they sometimes get lost and we have to order more.”

– Peter Inootik,
Pond Inlet, March 2023.

» **Lack of Road Infrastructure:** While some see potential for roads to connect communities and improve access to resources, others worry about environmental impacts on land and animals.

“It’s nice to think about having a road one day, but then all the things you have to think about that might have an impact on the environment, the people.... It’s kind of hard to say you really want something like that.”

– Hunter, Iqaluit,
February 2023.

“I think if we had a road to other provinces or even just in the territory, we would probably live here, we would just go out more. We wouldn’t feel trapped. We wouldn’t feel like we’re in a fish bowl. We’d have more options out there, but I think mostly the Elders would stay. Maybe we’d have more tourists.”

– Rosie Akavak,
Kimmirut, March 2023.

“Pond Inlet should have more roads to camping areas, like Ladies Lake. Very few people can go hunting just outside the town.”

– Kenan Issigaitak,
Pond Inlet,
March 2023.

» **Marine Infrastructure Needs and Concerns:** More harbors and docks are needed to support fishing, hunting, and economic opportunities. Lack of harbours increases cost of harvesting because boats are more easily damaged. Coastal erosion can be limited with the help of marine infrastructure.

“That’s what infrastructure we need here in order to sustain our harvesting for the ocean, for the land: We don’t have no dock or shelter. There are days that we can’t travel because the waves are huge trying to get out. once you pass the waves you can travel, but you can’t if you can’t get out.”

– Resident of Grise Fiord, April 2023.

“[The small craft harbour] was built just last year and it’s definitely been a help to local boaters and hunters. There’s going to be quite a few boats docked there this year. I noticed a few people finally started getting boats. (K: They didn’t have boats before?) No. Either due to shortage of the inventory or not enough money. But some people have been trying to save up and they finally have, so they bought a boat.”

– Aooloo Arreak, Pond Inlet, March 2023.

“For fisheries there needs to be a processing and storage building. because if we land the fish there is no storage place or processing, packaging place. And if we want to become a commercial food producer we have to follow the Canadian Food Inspection Agency.”

- Resident of Pond Inlet, March 2023.

3. Economic and Policy Considerations

Infrastructure development needs to align with Northern residents' aspirations and not redirect Northern life.

“And it's very dangerous to represent the recipients of the [land] claim simply by having [academic] credentials.”

- Hunter, Iqaluit, June 2023.

Community members highlighted the following areas for improvement:

» **E-commerce and Amazon:** Amazon has become an essential resource for many Nunavut residents, providing access to goods constrained by high costs and limited availability. Inuit residents adapt Amazon's services to navigate gaps left by government programs. The reliance on Amazon highlights the need to address the underlying issues of high prices and limited variety in local stores.

"It's not easy to get parts because there is no manufacturing in the north, all the parts come in from the south. And all the parts come in by freight, it is expensive and some parts, maybe if you can gather them in a bundle [it's less expensive] and that's once a year through sealift to our community. But it's different from Iqaluit, they have so many sealifts per summer. Here it's one to two times, two different shipping vessel but only one per company."

- Resident of Pond Inlet, March 2023.

"Any vehicle parts or tools that I can get through the hub, I'll get because those are ridiculously expensive locally. What's nice about parts is that a lot of the time, parts that are available on other websites are available on Amazon just the same: same parts, same quality, same brand. So, go through the hub if the shipping is three to five days."

- Resident of Iqaluit, May 2024.

» **Need for Multi-Year Funding:** Short-term grants and funding cycles create instability for food sovereignty initiatives as well as infrastructure development.

“The biggest issue we have is money, budget. We make plans at meetings, stuff like that, but they don’t always go forward with it. So the biggest issue we have is money.”

– Resident of Kimmirut,
March 2023.

» **Capacity Building and Training:** There is a strong need for local training in trades (electricians, mechanics, pilots, freezer technicians) to support infrastructure maintenance and economic independence. Programs need to be offered within the territory to reduce stress on families.

“I think we need more certified electricians, freezer technicians, plumbers... We need all the trades to help build this community. And to help fight food insecurity. Because education is the key to fight food insecurity.”

– Resident of Pond Inlet,
March 2023.

“We don’t have the human resources to properly run every aspect of the system that’s up here, put in place by Government of Canada through land claims, but they didn’t train the people and they don’t have the human resources to run all the jobs that are here. For example, right now, there’s about 35 to 40% vacancy of all the jobs here in Nunavut. All the high management jobs. There’s nobody up there.”

– Simeonie Akpalialuk,
Iqaluit, February 2023.

“To get a house, you need to have, like, five kids, or you’re practically homeless. You can go on the list, but then it would take, like, five years, or you would have to resubmit with other people. Because there’s only houses with, four, five rooms, three rooms, never one or two.”

– Resident of Resolute
Bay, April 2023.

» **Housing Policy and Allocation:** Points system for public housing is not transparent for many applicants. Young, financially successful, single residents experience barriers to get their own housing. There is a desire for more mixed housing that reflects various family/group/single dwelling needs.

“What would you dream for Pond?” “More housing.”

– Patrick Peterloosie, Pond Inlet, March 2023.

“You can’t afford housing if you’ve got a regular job. And if you can get a housing unit, then you can’t afford to pay because land developers, they charge way too much for an apartment. A person who’s working in labor can’t afford to rent one at all. The only type that they can get is social housing. And they’re so far behind, and there’s so many people who need that right now, because they can’t make enough money to rent like \$4,000 a month or \$3,500 a month.”

– Tommy Kanayak, Iqaluit, February 2023.

“There’s a lot of people that come in for work. That takes a big percentage [of housing]. Cause like the military that comes in, the workers that come in for ATCO, for management jobs, like at the Hamlet, at the store. Just a lot of people that have to get flown in. And then they take housing.”

– Resident of Resolute Bay, April 2023.

» **Role of External Actors:** Many decisionmakers live in the South but determine futures in the territory, which leads to a lack of nuance in policy and funding. Discussions around transport infrastructure increasingly consider local use and value alongside economic and political strategies, which is appreciated. Mining, conservation, tourism, and military investments are shaping infrastructure development, with mixed community responses.

“If President Biden wanted to visit Kimmirut, I think that’s the only way Kimmirut would get a bigger runway. That’s how Iqaluit got a runway, is by the military.”

– Resident of Kimmirut,
March 2023.

“We will want to benefit as much as everything surrounding us. They [the federal government] seek our support to protect it [the High Arctic Region]. But yet, because we’re not a hub for an airline we lose out all the time.”

– Resident of Grise Fiord,
April 2023.

“Tourism can be very good for Grise Fiord, as in other places. But tourism is, in its own way, a form of exploitation. Which is not always so great.”

– Larry Audlaluk, Grise Fiord, April 2023.

4. Future Directions and Community Priorities

Nunavummiut have clear priorities for the future, emphasizing the need for community-driven decision-making, infrastructure that serves local needs, and stronger support for traditional knowledge and food sovereignty. These priorities reflect a collective vision for a more self-determined and interconnected Nunavut, where planning and development align with Inuit values and realities.

“We’re told a lot of things. Not asked a lot, but told a lot.”

– Resident of Iqaluit,
February 2023.

Research participants spoke of many hurdles and suggestions, a selection of which are mentioned here:

» ***IQ Capacity Building:*** Support community-driven IQ programs for Inuit to expand social and sharing networks and improve navigational and harvesting knowledge, which support food sovereignty.

When you take people out and share skills, you know that their knowledge is capable of teaching someone else down the line. It’s there forever once you learn it. Like navigating to another community, that would be good knowledge to transfer country food from town to town.”

– Jeanine Nowdluk,
Iqaluit, February 2023.

“I’ve always said here in the North our work conditions should be changed. Where on good weather days, we have days off. And when it’s bad weather, we work. It doesn’t matter if it’s on a weekend or not. But meet the same number of days per month. And you have your 10 days a month of good weather days. You’ve already hunted, so now you have to work the rest. If we had that kind of system, that kind of work ethics would be great. The flexibility would be really great. It would actually increase your ability to harvest food for people in the community.”

- Simeonie Akpalialuk, Iqaluit, February 2023.

“But riding on a sled with your dog team, the sound it makes, they all have different names. The immense vocabulary of owning your Husky dog team went with the dog slaughter. And that’s the most effective and ensured way of passing the knowledge down so each family can have a food at their table. And at the same time carry on the wonderful practice of sharing the catch. Going out hunting is the most effective way.”

- Hunter, Iqaluit, June 2023.

“If our government is going to be honoring the claim, which is to make life better, the logical step to making life better up here, if you’re going to provide subsidy, you better demand cap on products. Instead of the company being given free will on how to use and apply that subsidy. That’s not making life better. That’s not being accountable as elected officials across Canada. We did not sign with Northern stores. We did not sign with Arctic Coops. We did not sign with Canadian North. We signed with federal government, territorial government, to make life better in the North.”

– Resident of Iqaluit,
June 2023.

» **Multi-Use Infrastructure:** Combine commercial, community, and resource development needs to maximize benefits. There is strong support for multi-use infrastructure, such as harbours that can accommodate both fishing vessels and smaller hunting boats, warehouses with community vehicle repair space, and resource development roads that allow access to hunting grounds.

“A lot of the infrastructure is only for work related things [like mining, community services] but it would be helpful if infrastructure could be used by everyone.”

– Alooos Arreak, Pond
Inlet, March 2023.

“We don’t have the infrastructure in place. If we did, we would have thriving fisheries. We would have things like a university that where we could do research. For example, alternative energy research we could be doing here in the cold environment. Nobody’s ever done that. All the alternative resources that have been developed in the south comes up here and fails. It’s not cut out for this environment.”

– Simeonie Akpalialuk,
Iqaluit, February 2023.

» **General Aviation Upgrades:** Improved navigation, weather instruments, and potential for a second airline focused on cargo transport. There is a need for more reliable transportation.

“Canadian North has to really knock on their heads and say, we cannot stop. We cannot have one flight per week for Grise. If we’re going to have one flight per week, let’s do five flights in that one day. (...) That’s going to hurt the tourism because the people who are coming up to tour won’t have room in the plane. Or they might be the only ones taking the plane and the people that want to come home are going to have to wait for next week.”

– Resident of Grise
Fiord, June 2023.

» **Desire for Increased Jet Service:** Many communities desire jet service and paved runways to improve connectivity, attract larger medical and educational opportunities, and support local economies.

“It’s the jet service to Resolute I want to see come back. Right now, the way the High Arctic is, ideal place for High Arctic headquarters? Pond Inlet. They should have jets go to Pond Inlet as well. Igloolik, Hall Beach, Pond Inlet, Clyde River, Resolute Bay and Grise Fiord - that’s the High Arctic. We need to have a hospital in Pond Inlet. The nearest hospital is in Iqaluit. It is urgent. And Pond Inlet? Perfect, has everything we need. And they can live off of the airline services that come out of Pond Inlet.”

– Larry Audlaluk, Grise Fiord, April 2023.

» **Expanding Country Food Networks:** Establishing a country food handling facility in Iqaluit could improve redistribution and reduce storage burdens at the airport. Offering a second airline that deals only with food distribution could reduce food insecurity. Making hunting a salary position would eliminate financial risk and support stability in country food access.

“Because medical travel is highly dependent on the airline travel it has taken up a lot of the transportation, and they take priority. And then when we try and look at food, that becomes secondary. And that’s why often a lot of the food that goes into the community is not fresh because of that priority. So there needs to be a change in how the infrastructure is used. Especially because the only way in and out of these communities is by airlines, and they got no choice. We need another airline that does not compete with this company, doesn’t do passengers, but services the food sector, primarily just the food sector. And that needs to be realized by all the partners. (...) I’m sure they have money to do something like that. The real issue is the will of these people to work together and make this happen.”

– Resident of Iqaluit, February 2023.

“We need to set up a network in every community with whatever food resources they can offer and their seasonality. And develop a network, whether it be Facebook or another system where everybody can connect on and have the ability to sell and trade food. And then have the transportation infrastructure along with that. It would help a lot of communities.”

– Simeonie Akpalialuk, Iqaluit, February 2023.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVING FOOD SOVEREIGNTY AND TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE IN NUNAVUT

1. Support for Country Food Access and Distribution

- » Support the creation of **community-run country food stores** in Iqaluit and other major hubs and establish an official **sharing network**.
- » Provide **long-term funding** for community freezers and subsidize maintenance, especially in smaller communities.
- » **Continue and expand on stable funding programs** such as the Nunavut Harvesters Support Program and Nauttiqsuqtiit.
- » Develop **regional cold storage hubs** not connected to the airline (e.g., a country food handling facility in Iqaluit, Rankin Inlet, Pond Inlet or Resolute Bay) to improve redistribution across Nunavut.

2. Transportation Policy Changes

- » Modify **Canadian North's cargo subsidy policies to allow cooperatives and small businesses** (e.g., Sedna's Lair, QCFC) to access flat-rate pricing.
- » Ensure that country food shipments are properly stored and **compensate harvesters** for spoiled or lost cargo.
- » Improve **weather monitoring, navigation and communication systems** at airports to reduce flight cancellations and delays.
- » Support **regional air cargo expansion**, potentially through a second airline or cargo service focused on food and essential goods.
- » Reduce **disproportionate cargo costs** for intra-community shipments (e.g., shipping from Resolute Bay to Grise Fiord should not be more expensive than to Ottawa).

3. Infrastructure Development Strategies

- » **Nunavummiut-Centered Planning:** More transparency in all stages of planning process. Offer a variety of ways to engage and share concerns/desires.
- » Prioritize **multi-use infrastructure** (small craft harbors, repair shops, storage spaces) to serve both economic and community needs.
- » Focus on strengthening **intra-territorial networks** to improve connections between communities.
- » **Expand community storage capacity** to improve resilience against food shortages and logistical delays.
- » Require **joint-use agreements** that ensure military and resource sector infrastructure (e.g., airstrips, roads, ports) serves local communities as well.

4. Economic and Workforce Development

- » Establish **Nunavut-based training programs** for aviation, mechanics, and trades to reduce dependence on fly-in workers from the South.
- » Support **high school trades and apprenticeship programs** to train local residents in maintaining transport and storage infrastructure.
- » Encourage **multi-year funding models** for sustainable food sovereignty initiatives.
- » Support **community economic initiatives** and smaller-scale territorial projects to address the high cost of food and limited variety in local stores to reduce reliance on external sources like Amazon.

5. Social Work and Relationship Building

- » **Engage directly with Nunavut communities** through long-term partnerships, and make the effort to connect with residents beyond the usual group by offering multiple ways to get involved/voice one's opinion.
- » Consolidate **information about proposed and ongoing projects into a database available to the public** to reduce information overflow and fatigue while increasing transparency.
- » **Collaborate with airlines, local businesses, and Inuit organizations** to ensure policies are effectively implemented, even beyond the project runtime.
- » **Promote Inuit-led futures** by disrupting imaginaries inundated with settler-colonial perspectives and instead encouraging Nunavummi Inuit to imagine what futures they want for their own communities.

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